

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF INTERNAL QUALITY ASSURANCE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF GRADUATES

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the phenomenon of the low quality of graduates produced by universities. BPS data proves that in 2022 universities will contribute 9.39% of the unemployment rate in Indonesia. This starts from the low quality assurance culture that exists in higher education. The general aim of this research is to describe and analyze strategic management of internal quality assurance in improving the quality of graduates in higher education. Specifically, this research aims to describe and analyze 1) strategic environment, 2) strategic formulation, 3) strategic implementation, 4) strategic evaluation, 5) strategic obstacles, and 6) solutions to strategic obstacles. The research method uses qualitative with a descriptive study approach. Data collection techniques use interviews, observation and documentation studies. The grand theory in this research is in accordance with Whellen and Hunger's opinion about strategic management, the middle theory uses Joseph Juran's opinion about total quality management, and the operational theory uses Edward Deming about quality. The research results specifically show that strategic management of internal quality assurance in improving the quality of college graduates is: 1) strategic environmental analysis carried out using strength, weakness, opportunity and threat (SWOT) analysis to analyze strength, weakness, opportunity and threat factors, 2) strategic formulation is carried out by formulating a vision and mission, determining institutional goals, developing strategies, and establishing policy guidelines, 3) strategic implementation is contained in the development program of 8 national education standards, 4) strategic evaluation is carried out programmatically through monitoring and evaluation activities, evaluation school self, accreditation and performance evaluation, 5) obstacles in strategic implementation lie in the lack of a quality culture, lack of human resources for internal quality auditors, weak control and improvement processes, 6) the solution to these obstacles can be done by developing a quality culture with 6 value systems (theological, logical, physiological, ethical, aesthetic and teleological). The research results generally show that strategic management of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates has been implemented, but has not provided maximum impact.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Internal Quality Assurance, Graduate Quality.

INTRODUCTION

The realization of the noble duties of higher education in accordance with the mandate of the law is to implement the Tri Dharma Higher Education program, namely the implementation of teaching, research and community service activities as an important role in educating the life of the nation and creating a generation of superior and

characterful people. This is in accordance with Law No. 12 of 2012 concerning higher education where Article 1 paragraph 9 states that universities have a non-negotiable obligation to implement the Tri Dharma (Law No. 12 concerning Higher Education, 2012).

The first task in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education is the implementation of teaching where universities are obliged to carry out teaching and education in accordance with the curriculum established in higher education, whether within the academy, polytechnic, high school, university or other forms. In a broad sense, the implementation of teaching and education is a conscious and planned effort as a form of self-development, both hard skills and soft skills, in accordance with the guidelines or rules that apply in the world of higher education with the aim of developing the potential that exists within oneself. If the teaching and education process carried out by a university can run well, it will have an impact on the output and outcomes of the university so that it can prepare its graduates to be able to answer all the challenges of changing times. If the teaching and education process is not prepared carefully then this will be directly proportional to the output of universities who will only be spectators when others have moved forward. Thus, the role of implementing teaching and education is an important factor for universities to carry out well.

The second task in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education is to carry out research and innovation and development. This is a very natural thing for universities to do, where universities are a place for academics, practitioners and professionals who are critical, creative and innovative to create something new through research and innovation activities that can have a real impact on society. The elements of research and innovation can also be used as indicators for developed countries in the world to be able to compete globally, therefore the Indonesian state is aggressively encouraging universities to be able to carry out research and publication in reputable international journals as a form of contribution to the nation's progress. research findings that can have a positive impact on the progress of the education sector. ideology, politics, social, health, economics and other sectors for the benefit of world society. Therefore, this research element is a necessity for educators to collaborate with students to find new findings in the world of research according to their respective fields of expertise.

The third task in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education is to carry out community service activities to be able to find out problems directly in society and participate in providing solutions to problems that arise with creative ideas and accurate anticipatory steps as a form of application of the expected theory. In this community service activity, universities can also collaborate with the pentahelix (5 important elements) in society, namely elements of government, the private sector, the industrial world, the business world, and universities themselves. This is an important point for establishing higher education milestones in society. A superior university is a university that has a real role and contributes to increasing the community development index and its benefits and benefits are felt in society.

If these three main and noble tasks are carried out in a planned, organized, implemented and maximally supervised manner, they will produce superior quality graduates and can exceed graduate competency standards set by the government which are used as the main reference in developing learning content standards and process standards. learning, learning assessment standards, standards for educators and education personnel, standards for facilities and infrastructure, learning management standards, and learning financing standards which serve as a reference for higher education institutions to carry out activities in accordance with standard criteria or can even exceed predetermined standards.

Furthermore, Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the education system states that higher education must be implemented with an open system that can be enjoyed by all groups who have met academic and administrative requirements (Razak et al., 2016). Law Number 20 of 2003 also states that the national education system is a whole component of education that is mutually sustainable in an integrated manner in order to achieve the national goals of education to be able to increase abilities and improve the quality of life of the community and the dignity of the Indonesian nation in the global arena (Law No. 20 About the National Education System, 2003). This can be in line with the ability of higher education institutions to manage and develop higher education institutions that use the principles of openness, modernity, and are always oriented towards good outcomes and the quality of competitive higher education products.

Referring to this statement, the essence of the higher education quality assurance system is that it boils down to continuous improvements to be able to improve the quality of graduates who can be ready for use by users and can create jobs so that they can benefit themselves, their families and the surrounding environment as agents of change. for national and global society.

To be able to produce quality and useful people, sustainable development in the higher education sector is the most important part, therefore higher education must be implemented in a more planned, organized and well-programmed manner in accordance with the mandate of Law Number 20 of 2003 where the system National education must be able to guarantee equal distribution of educational opportunities, improve the quality and relevance and efficiency of education management to face challenges in accordance with the demands of local, national and global changes so that it is necessary to reform education in a planned, directed and sustainable manner (Law No. 20 concerning Systems National Education, 2003).

Quoting this, the meaning of the national education system must be able to explain the education development sector which will face three serious challenges, namely 1) equality and access to quality education, 2) increasing quality, relevance and competitiveness and, 3) improving quality education management, increasing effectiveness and efficiency in education management.

The role and objectives of higher education are also stated in Government Regulation Number 60 of 1999 concerning higher education where in paragraph 2 states that the goal of higher education is to prepare students to become educated people who have intellectual and/or professional abilities who can implement, develop, and/or can expand the scientific treasures possessed in the fields of science, technology and art. Then the next goal is that universities are expected to be able to improve people's standard of living and be able to participate in enriching Indonesian national culture (Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 60 concerning Higher Education, 1999).

Nowadays, universities are actually facing various kinds of big challenges, therefore higher education institutions are required to carry out more innovations in various fields in facing the era of society 5.0. Apart from that, universities must also be a place to study that is conducive for students and a comfortable home for scientists to produce innovative research output. Universities must also be able to create future leaders and professionals. Therefore, universities must be required to squeeze their brains, energy and thoughts to be able to answer various challenges of changing times. Then this will have an impact on reforms in the higher education management sector so that it can support collaborative learning processes, innovative scientific development, as well as creative and responsible community service activities in accordance with changing times and the needs for the use of science and technology today.

On the other hand, quality is also an important issue in the world of national education. Universities are required to carry out their role in developing academic and scientific culture with transparent and accountable higher education governance. Higher education governance must also be able to create freedom of academic and scientific platforms for the entire academic community so that they can grow and develop optimally to become reliable academics and scientists. Referring to this, the government gave the green light in accordance with the rules and norms that apply to higher education institutions for the concept of autonomy in managing higher education institutions to partially improve the quality and qualities of higher education institutions in order to fulfill society's expectations of higher education stakeholders.

The quality of college graduates is also an important milestone in producing superior human resources so that all efforts and efforts to improve the quality of college graduates must be carried out on an ongoing basis. However, in the business field it is felt that it has not had a real impact, where in general the indicators for the quality of graduates only use the cumulative achievement index or GPA, the student's length of study and graduation honors. However, to be able to achieve superior quality of graduates, universities also need to ensure that they can improve the competence and skills of graduates by entering the world of work or creating jobs. If these efforts and efforts are successful, the community will definitely have more trust in the university.

The issue of graduate quality is also a central issue that is always interesting and hot to be sought for solutions by various groups and education observers. The quality of national graduates currently also satisfies all parties, especially university graduate users. Therefore, in facing the era of society 5.0, the quality and qualities of each higher

education management and its elements must be able to think in a planned and sustainable manner so that the quality of the higher education graduates they manage can increase and the results of research and dedication of the academic community are able to meet the needs and demands of an increasingly modern era. complex.

One effort to improve the quality of higher education graduates is to build and implement an internal quality assurance system for higher education so that the vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMTS) of higher education can be achieved effectively and efficiently. Modern universities must be able to create a culture of quality that has characteristics and advantages to be competitive.

The increasing number of new universities and the establishment of new study programs are also required to be able to demonstrate the quality of graduates that can be accepted by society as expected by the business and industrial world as well as the government and private sector. The increase in tertiary institutions also has the potential to cause the quality of graduates to decline sharply considering that many tertiary institutions consider that the internal quality assurance system is not the main goal in managing tertiary institutions, but still think that the most important thing for tertiary institutions is to obtain the quantity or number of students or student body.

The central phenomenon in this research is related to higher education quality assurance which has not yet been carried out or accredited by BAN-PT or the Independent Accreditation Institute (LAM) and the Internal Quality Assurance System which has not yet fully referred to the higher education quality assurance system or SPM-PT. From preliminary studies conducted at the research locus, currently various efforts have been made to improve the quality of graduates but in reality they are still not integrated and still use self-made guidelines or criteria, for example in terms of recruitment, coaching systems, promotions, rotations, demotions. lecturers and educational staff as well as structural positions in higher education. This kind of management causes conditions in the organizational culture that are less conducive, which will impact the quality of lecturers and educational staff that are not the same because they do not use clear and uniform measures, which results in the quality of graduates not being in line with expectations. This phenomenon must be able to be overcome by higher education administrators so that the quality of higher education graduates can be in accordance with the wishes of graduate users. One effort to overcome this phenomenon is to implement a quality assurance system and apply strict criteria to exceed predetermined quality standards.

METHODS

This research is qualitative research using a descriptive study approach. Qualitative research is research proposed to understand social phenomena from the participant's point of view or perspective. Qualitative is an approach to conducting research that is oriented towards natural phenomena or symptoms. Qualitative is data that is presented in the form of verbal words, not in the form of numbers. The aim of qualitative research is to create a systematic, factual and accurate description, picture or painting of the facts, properties and relationships between the phenomena being investigated. In the

qualitative research process, a researcher's skill in building communication with informants is one of the key factors for the success of the research. Therefore, a qualitative researcher is required to have high sensitivity and astuteness so that he is able to find detailed facts related to the problem he is researching.

This research seeks to fully describe the process of improving the quality of college graduates in improving and developing the quality of higher education, so that the higher education learning process is able to give birth to a generation that is capable, tough, creative so that it is able to make a real contribution to the development of the times, and can also contribute real to build society in this country.

In order for the substance of research to be revealed, in-depth observation of natural objects is required, namely objects that develop as they are, not manipulated by researchers. The qualitative approach is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior. According to them, this approach is directed at the setting and the individual or organization into variables or hypotheses, but needs to view them as part of a whole

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Strategic Environment

There is a need for the involvement of education stakeholders including the community, business world, industry, academics, government, private sector and media in conducting environmental studies as a basis for strategic planning so that the results of the formulation become more in-depth and comprehensive for the needs of various groups and have positive implications for effectiveness. management of higher education that can meet the expectations of its service users. The results of SWOT analysis in a strategic environment have not yet been optimally used by leaders of research-located higher education institutions to be able to maximize all strengths and reduce or even eliminate weak factors and then be able to maximally take advantage of opportunities and face challenges in internal quality assurance in improving the quality of graduates in higher education institutions.

2. Strategic Formulation

To be able to realize strategic formulation, it is necessary to have complete information about the various factors that can influence it. Currently, SWOT analysis studies are considered the most effective for formulating strategic planning, where policy holders must be able to control strength and weakness factors in order to be able to take maximum advantage of opportunities and swiftly face all threats that arise. The strategic planning that has been prepared is then evaluated periodically in accordance with the results of environmental analysis through the assumption of SO, WO, ST and WT strategies which will have positive implications for more effective strategic planning to produce superior quality higher education graduates in accordance with current demands and future era. The strategic formulation of internal quality assurance for higher education in improving the quality of graduates carried out by both research loci is carried out by 1)

formulating a vision and mission, 2) determining institutional goals, 3) developing strategies, and 4) establishing policy guidelines contained in the manual policy guidelines quality, quality standards, strategic plans and forms which are used as guidelines as a result of the strategic formulation carried out by the two research loci.

3. Strategic Implementation

The strategic implementation of internal quality assurance in improving the quality of graduates carried out by both research loci is carried out by referring to 8 national education standards carried out through strategic steps with clear and standardized operational procedures, support for budget allocations, and effective, efficient, transparent management, and accountable. This has a significant impact on internal quality assurance in higher education so that it can lead to improving the quality of superior graduates.

4. Strategic Evaluation

Strategic evaluation aims to ensure the work system can be carried out sustainably through prevention with the hope that there will be no errors and continuous improvement in a planned and programmed manner. Supervision of the planning and implementation of school programs has positive implications for efficiency, effectiveness and productivity in achieving school goals without misuse and abuse of authority or budget. Strategic evaluation is carried out based on 8 national education standards and has a simultaneous impact on the control and improvement stages carried out by universities in carrying out internal quality assurance to create quality graduates.

5. Strategic Constraints

Obstacles in implementing strategic management of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates lie in the lack of formation of a quality culture in higher education, achievement motivation which still needs to be improved, lack of auditor resources, limited financial resources, and weak control and improvement processes. and there needs to be strong support from foundation institutions to encourage the acceleration of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates.

6. Solutions to Strategic Constraints

Solutions to strategic obstacles in internal quality assurance in improving the quality of graduates include that universities must have basic guidelines that regulate various aspects of education management that are easy to read and learn, schools must have a curriculum as a guide for managing higher education operations, have a formulation of vision, mission, goals, quality goals and targets that refer to the development of 8 national education standards. Then universities are also required to always involve the participation of all stakeholders, the academic community, parents and the community, prioritizing the development of student attitudes or character which is based on 6 value systems, namely; theological, physical-physiological, ethical, aesthetic, logical-realistic, teleological in every aspect of life, an IT-based university management information

system or learning management system, having qualified human resources in their field, having a shared commitment to always be oriented towards customer satisfaction, carrying out continuous improvement through the implementation of strategic management with an integrated quality management approach or total quality management (TQM).

CONCLUSION

The strategic environmental analysis of internal quality assurance of higher education institutions in improving the quality of graduates carried out at both research loci is in accordance with strategic management theory which includes internal environmental analysis, external environmental analysis, as well as SWOT analysis (which includes strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) to be able to Analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that arise.

The strategic formulation of higher education internal quality assurance in improving the quality of graduates is in accordance with strategic management theory which is implemented by formulating a vision and mission, setting institutional goals, developing strategies, and establishing policy guidelines.

The strategic implementation of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates carried out in both research loci is in accordance with strategic management theory and has been contained in 8 national educational standards which include graduate competency standards, content standards, process standards, learning assessment standards, educator standards and educational personnel, facilities and infrastructure standards, management standards, and financing standards.

The strategic evaluation of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates carried out at both research loci has been carried out in accordance with strategic management theory which is implemented programmatically starting from monitoring and evaluation, self-evaluation, accreditation and performance evaluation, as well as measurement at the control and improvement stage for can exceed established standards.

Obstacles in the implementation of strategic management of internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates carried out in both research loci include quality culture factors that have not yet been optimally formed, managerial, limited resources for internal quality auditors, and the financing side which has not been able to accommodate everything. the need for internal quality assurance, as well as the results of internal quality audits which are still not being felt optimally in the control and improvement process so that negative events that occur can recur in the future.

Solutions to obstacles in the implementation of strategic management for internal quality assurance in higher education in improving the quality of graduates are carried out by both research loci in an anticipatory manner using a collaborative, cooperative approach so that each actor appointed to carry out strategic management policies can carry out their duties, principal and functions in accordance with standards that have been set to

improve the quality of graduates. Apart from that, the relevant stakeholders are also required to take a role in being able to work together rationally, systematically, planned, organized and controlled and committed together in achieving the vision, mission, goals and objectives set by the university. Apart from that, this will also encourage the entire academic community to accelerate their achievements, always be oriented towards customer satisfaction, and build a quality culture in higher education based on six value systems, namely theological, logical, physiological, ethical, aesthetic and teleological values). Solutions to the obstacles faced by research loci are also carried out by conducting workshops, in-house training, training, and bringing in experts to increase the competency and capacity of leaders to produce graduates of superior quality and competitiveness. Meanwhile, the curative solution to the obstacles that occur is by providing rewards for those who excel and warnings for those whose performance is felt to be not optimal in order to encourage a culture of quality in higher education.

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